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Data Review

Data Citation

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Abstract

ILOSTAT is the statistical data collection of the International Labour Organization's Department of Statistics. With ILOSTAT the ILO Department of Statistics aims to "provide relevant, timely and comparable labour statistics, develop international standards for better measurement of labour, and help member states develop and improve their labour statistics". It provides free access to more than 1700 labour-related indicators with over 250 million data points.

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Data Review – ILOSTAT

ILOSTAT is the statistical data collection of the International Labour Organization's Department of Statistics. It provides free access to more than 250 million data points (1). Featuring a wide range of labour topics, it is the focal point for labour statistics to the UN (2). The ILOSTAT experts "compile and produce labour statistics, with the goal of disseminating internationally-comparable datasets" (2). With ILOSTAT the ILO Department of Statistics aims to "provide relevant, timely and comparable labour statistics, develop international standards for better measurement of labour, and help member states develop and improve their labour statistics" (2).

Key features:

ILOSTAT provides "comprehensive international data across a wide range of labour-related topics" (3). There are multiple ways to access ILOSTAT data. The topic catalogue makes it easy to find relevant indicators on a specific topic. Some topics offer graphics or diagrams. Alternatively, you can view all the indicators available for a specific country via the country catalogue or even all available indicators via the indicator catalogue. The corresponding data can then be downloaded in the desired format (.csv, .dta, .xlsx) or displayed via the ILOSTAT Data Explorer.

The Data Explorer is an "intuitive interface to filter, reshape and download data" (4). Data for all indicators is available there. "Reshape" refers to the "calculate distributions", "calculate growth rates" and "pivot" functions. However, the first two are not available for all indicators. There is an option to save the created table using the "Bookmark" function and retrieve it later. Alternatively, the created table can also be saved as a PDF or Excel file using the "Capture View" function. The data explorer also allows you to view information about the data set to which the indicator belongs. The data set is described there, and the topic, time span, and number of data points are specified. The data sets are continuously updated. The latest update is noted in the data set description.

Individual or all data sets can be downloaded via the bulk download facility. This includes data, metadata, and documentation (5). Other ways of working with ILOSTAT data include the Excel add-in and R package, which allow you to access ILOSTAT data directly in your statistical software (6).

The country profiles “focus on headline indicators (a subset of the available data)” and give national figures for the latest available year (7).

Indicators:

The indicators offered by ILOSTAT are divided into broad topics (see table 1). These, in turn, are separated into three to four more specific labour-related sub-topics. The sub-topics vary considerably in terms of the number of indicators included. The range of available indicators varies between 1 and 405. In total ILOSTAT offers over 1700 indicators (8). Due to the adoption of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), 14 SDG-indicators were established to enable monitoring of the goals (9).

Table 1: Indicators

Topic	Sub-topics (indicators)
Featured	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Sustainable development (18) ● Child labour (35) ● Unpaid work (6) ● ILO sectors (352)
Labour supply	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Population and labour force (157) ● Employment (213) ● Unemployment and labour underutilization (347)
Working conditions and labour rights	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Wages (27) ● Working time (127) ● Safety and health at work (17) ● Social dialogue (6)
Poverty and inequality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Working poverty (2) ● Labour income and inequality (4) ● Informal economy (405) ● Social protection (1)
Productivity and prices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Labour productivity (5) ● Labour costs (3) ● Inflation (9)
Selected groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Migrant workers (69) ● Youth (62) ● Women (96) ● Volunteer workers (6)

The data coverage per country for the countries relevant to Discuss Data varies a lot. These countries include Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Estonia, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Latvia, Lithuania, Moldova, Russia, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Ukraine,

and Uzbekistan. A random sample of 30 indicators selected for review showed that data for all countries was available in five cases. In 17 cases data was available for most countries (9-14/15), in three cases data was available for half of the countries (7-8/15) and in five cases data was missing for most countries (1-6/15). There was no case where all relevant countries had no data for the selected indicator. However, it is important to note that this does not automatically imply that the countries are comparable for every indicator, as the available data points vary significantly due to differences in the time series considered. In most cases, data from the last ten years is available. Please note that for certain indicators, data is only available for a specific year for some countries. Turkmenistan, Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan have the lowest data coverage (see table 2).

Data Collection:

To collect and compile all the data ILOSTAT offers, three main methods are used: microdata processing, automated data collection and the annual ILOSTAT questionnaire (3).

For the microdata processing “the ILO collects the underlying household survey datasets (...) compiled by national statistical offices” (3). After collection, “ILO experts systematically process them to generate harmonized indicators based on international standards” (3).

The International Conference of Labour Statisticians (ICLS) is the body that establishes international standards for labour statistics (2). In this regard, the International Labour Organization's Department of Statistics is actively testing surveys to ensure the production of high-quality data (2).

The automated data collection involves “data from national statistical offices around the world” (3). ILOSTATs automation process includes “systematizing the collection of data from a wide variety of online data repositories and reshaping, reprocessing and validating the data before publishing on ILOSTAT” (3).

The annual ILOSTAT questionnaire is an Excel-based questionnaire that is sent out annually to national statistical offices and labour ministries. It is an “important data collection tool to obtain information for countries with limited dissemination platforms as well as non-household survey data, which are often unavailable online” (3).

In addition to the three main methods, there are also the ILO modelled estimates and projections, the “world’s largest repository of internationally comparable national,

regional and global estimates of key labour indicators” (3). The ILO experts review the input data to ensure only internationally comparable data are included and for missing data they use econometric models to produce estimates. Using the same method, future projections are provided.

Table 2: Data availability for relevant countries (as of 23 September 2025) (3, 5)

Country	Data channels for latest year available since 2017	Available Data
Armenia	Microdata + Questionnaire	Annually since 1985: - 31 subjects - 968 indicators - 1.205.151 records
Azerbaijan	Questionnaire only	Annually since 1981: - 23 subjects - 170 indicators - 93.639 records
Belarus	Questionnaire only	Annually since 1970 (first data 1959): - 26 subjects - 538 indicators - 453.248 records
Estonia	Automated + Microdata + Questionnaire	Annually since 1980: - 29 subjects - 779 indicators - 1.611.640 records
Georgia	Microdata + Questionnaire	Annually since 1990: - 32 subjects - 829 indicators - 793.452 records
Kazakhstan	Automated + Questionnaire	Annually since 1982: - 24 subjects - 147 indicators - 66.066 records
Kyrgyzstan	Microdata + Questionnaire	Annually since 1983: - 27 subjects - 570 indicators - 697.603 records
Latvia	Automated + Microdata + Questionnaire	Annually since 1987: - 28 subjects - 743 indicators - 1.555.021 records
Lithuania	Automated + Microdata + Questionnaire	Annually since 1983: - 28 subjects - 750 indicators - 1.474.380 records

Moldova	Microdata + Questionnaire	Annually since 1981: - 29 subjects - 879 indicators - 2.107.164 records
Russia	Microdata + Questionnaire	Annually since 1980: - 29 subjects - 618 indicators - 1.159.608 records
Tajikistan	Questionnaire only	Annually since 1990: - 27 subjects - 789 indicators - 285.877 records
Turkmenistan	No incoming data	Annually since 1990: - 15 subjects - 88 indicators - 28.119 records
Ukraine	Automated + Microdata + Questionnaire	Annually since 1969 (first data 1959): - 28 subjects - 412 indicators - 192.574 records
Uzbekistan	Questionnaire only	Annually since 1990: - 24 subjects - 245 indicators - 50.037 records

Access and Funding:

Due to the Fundamental Principles of Official Statistics ILOSTAT data are free to use and do not require a registration (1).

The International Labour Organization that operates ILOSTAT, is funded through three main sources: “the Regular Budget, funded from assessed contributions by Member States” of the United Nations; “the Regular Budget Supplementary Account, funded by voluntary contributions from key partners”; and “voluntary contributions from over 140 funding partners, including public and private organizations” (10).

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